

Serum and Urinary Electrolytes in Health and Disease: An Overview

Erhunmwunse RU¹, Ogbodo EC²

¹Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, Benson Idahosa University, Benin City, Nigeria

²Department of Clinical Chemistry, Faculty of Medical Laboratory Science, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Anambra State, Nigeria

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
25 July 2025

Corresponding Author:
Ogbodo EC

ABSTRACT

The human body is an amazing machine, with mechanisms that keep fluid balance, electroneutrality and pH within relatively narrow ranges. Electrolytes are essential in this process because they control fluid volume, osmotic pressure, acid-base balance, cardiac cell contractibility, and neuromuscular cell excitability. Electrolytes include sodium, potassium, magnesium, calcium, and phosphorus are required for proper metabolic reactions and homeostasis. They work together to maintain cell membrane function, neuron conductivity, muscle contraction, hormone activity, bone structure, and fluid and acid-base balance. Electrolyte imbalances can be life-threatening, thus maintaining homeostasis is essential for overall health. This review examined the role of serum and urine electrolytes in health and disease, focusing on their roles, composition, and complex regulatory processes involved in achieving osmotic equilibrium, fluid and electrolyte balance, diseases, risk factors, laboratory diagnosis, and management.

KEYWORDS: Electrolytes, Functions, Composition, Regulation, Body fluid and electrolyte balance, Electrolyte imbalance, disorders of electrolytes, risk factors, laboratory diagnosis and management.

INTRODUCTION

The human body is an amazing machine, with mechanisms that keep fluid balance, electroneutrality, and pH within relatively narrow ranges. Electrolytes, or ions with an electric charge, are important in this process because they regulate fluid volume, osmotic pressure, acid-base balance, myocardial cell contractibility, and neuromuscular cell excitability (Open Resources for Nursing, 2021; Dunne, 2023). Water makes up over 60% of the body's weight, and it is often separated into two primary compartments: intracellular fluid (ICF) and extracellular fluid ((Brinkman *et al.*, 2023). The interstitial fluid (fluid between and around cells) and the intravascular fluid (plasma) are the two subsets of the extracellular fluid (ECF), which is primarily made up of sodium ions (Na⁺) and chloride ions (Tobias *et al.*, 2022). The ICF, which is located within the cell membrane, makes up approximately 66% of total body water and is primarily made up of potassium ions (K⁺), phosphate ions (PO₄⁻), and magnesium (Mg²⁺) (Internet lectures, 2011).

Electrolytes are inorganic chemicals that break down into ions in solution and gain the ability to conduct electricity. Example of electrolytes include sodium, potassium, calcium, chloride, and phosphate. Sodium is the most abundant ion in extracellular fluid, and it contributes significantly to blood osmolarity or solute concentration.

Electrolytes (sodium, potassium, magnesium, calcium, and phosphorus) are needed for appropriate metabolic responses and homeostasis. Electrolytes operate together to maintain cell membrane function, neuron conductivity, muscular contractility, hormone activity, bone structure, and fluid and acid-base balance (Dunne, 2023). Renal function controls both serum electrolyte balance and normal balance (Meyers, 2009; Blackmer, 2018). Normal processes maintain the electrolyte balance. However, clinical conditions and drugs can produce electrolyte imbalances. When analyzing electrolytes, three main processes guide therapy: discover the reason, define it as acute or chronic, and devise a treatment strategy to address the electrolyte anomaly.

OSMOTIC EQUILIBRIUM

The body maintains osmotic homeostasis by three key principles: hydrostatic pressure, which promotes ultrafiltration in the kidney's nephrons.

Oncotic pressure prevents fluid and solute migration into the nephron's lumen through protein molecules like albumin, while capillary permeability promotes filtration. Solute composition differences are due to sodium (the main extracellular cation), potassium (the primary intracellular cation), and the sodium-potassium-adenosine triphosphatase (Na⁺-K⁺-ATPase) pump, which uses

Fig 1: Compartments of Total Body Water

cellular energy to maintain sodium and potassium concentrations (Jain, 2015; O'Brien, 2014; Schmidt, 2010). Osmotic pressure regulates the distribution of water between the ECF and ICF. O'Brien (2014) identifies two factors that influence this distribution: (1) transmembrane ion channels

and electrochemical gradients, and (2) semi-permeable membranes that maintain osmotic equilibrium. Cellular membranes are relatively impermeable to large anions and proteins but are freely permeable to water.

Table 1: Electrolytes Distribution (Cations)

Electrolytes	ECF concentration (mEq/L)	ICF concentration (mEq/L)	Functions
Sodium	142	10	Fluid balance, osmotic pressure.
Potassium	5	100	Neuromuscular excitability, acid-base balance.
Calcium	5	—	Bones, blood clotting
Magnesium	2	123	Enzymes
Total Positive Ions	154	205	

Table 2: Electrolytes Distribution (Anions)

Electrolytes	ECF concentration (mEq/L)	ICF concentration (mEq/L)	Functions
Chloride	105	2	Fluid balance, osmotic pressure.
Bicarbonate	24	8	Acid-base balance.
Proteins	16	55	Osmotic pressure
Phosphate	2	149	Energy storage
Sulphate	1	—	Protein metabolism
Total negative ions	154	205	

REGULATION OF FLUID AND ELECTROLYTE BALANCE

The kidneys play an important role in maintaining fluid and electrolyte balance by managing the amount and composition of urine (Dalal *et al.*, 2023; Scott *et al.*, 2023). Three hormones have important roles in controlling fluid and

electrolyte balance. The body produces three hormones: antidiuretic hormone from the pituitary gland, aldosterone from the adrenal cortex, and atrial natriuretic peptide from the heart.

ANTIDIURETIC HORMONE (ADH)

ADH, also known as arginine vasopressin, is a peptide hormone that regulates body water levels and inhibits fluid loss (Cuzzo *et al.*, 2023). The term antidiuretic is derived from the words anti (against) and diuresis (fluid loss). The major stimulation for ADH production from the posterior pituitary gland is an increase in blood osmolarity (in other words, increased solute concentration and decreased water concentration) (Yasir and Mechanic, 2023). Osmoreceptors are specialized neurons in the hypothalamus that sense changes in blood osmolarity (Maher and Macnab, 2018). ADH increases water reabsorption in the kidney's distal

convoluted tubules and collecting ducts (Essa and Macnab, 2021). This technique ultimately conserves water. Under these conditions, a little amount of extremely concentrated urine (hypertonic) is expelled.

Another function of ADH is to increase thirst. As a result, water intake increases, lowering blood osmolarity and aiding in the restoration of homeostasis (Essa and Macnab, 2021). If ADH is absent, as in diabetes insipidus, the kidney's water reabsorption is drastically reduced, and enormous volumes of dilute urine are voided, up to 25 liters per day (German and Stanfield, 2016).

Fig 2: Diagrammatic representation of the release and mechanism of action of ADH (Klabunde, 2021).

ALDOSTERONE

Aldosterone is a hormone that controls blood sodium levels. Aldosterone particularly stimulates sodium reabsorption in the distal convoluted tubule and collecting duct of the nephrons in the kidney (Scott, 2023; Tsilosani *et al.*, 2022). This process conserves sodium. Because "water follows salt," this may result in water retention when ADH is present. Another function of aldosterone is to enhance the kidney's release of potassium, resulting in a reduction in blood and an increase in urine. An increase in potassium (mainly) or a reduction in sodium in the blood reaching the adrenal cortex directly stimulates the release of aldosterone (Tsilosani *et al.*, 2022).

Activation of the renin-angiotensin system also stimulates aldosterone secretion (Tsilosani *et al.*, 2022). In this process, the kidney's juxtaglomerular cells produce renin in response to a decrease in blood volume, a decrease in blood pressure, or activation by the sympathetic nervous system. Renin is an enzyme that converts a plasma protein called angiotensinogen into angiotensin I. Angiotensin I is then converted by angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) into angiotensin II (Martini *et al.*, 2015). Angiotensin II has two main actions: 1) it promotes aldosterone secretion from the adrenal cortex, leading to salt reabsorption and conservation, and 2) it produces vasoconstriction, raising blood pressure. These mechanisms restore equilibrium.

Fig 3: The Aldosterone Feedback Loop (Wikimedia, 2023).

Aldosterone, which is released by the adrenal gland, facilitates reabsorption of Na^+ and thus the reabsorption of water.

Fig 4: The Renin-Angiotensin System (Burnell and Turner, 2025). Angiotensin II stimulates the release of aldosterone from the adrenal cortex.

ATRIAL NATRIURETIC PEPTIDE (ANP)

The natriuretic peptide family is made up of three biologically active peptides: atrial natriuretic peptide (ANP), brain (or B-type) natriuretic peptide (BNP), and C-type natriuretic peptide (Nakagawa *et al.*, 2019). Among these, the heart secretes ANP and BNP, which function as cardiac hormones. ANP is a hormone that promotes both fluid and sodium loss by the kidneys. Human ANP has three molecular forms, α -ANP, β -ANP, and proANP (or γ -ANP), with proANP predominating in healthy atrial tissue. The name natriuretic

actually means “salt excreting.” ANP release from the atria is stimulated when blood volume and pressure are elevated (Sherwood, 2013). ANP has three major effects (Curry, 2005; Nakagawa *et al.*, 2019):

- 1) It decreases aldosterone release, resulting in a decrease in sodium reabsorption and increased sodium loss in the urine,
- 2) It decreases ADH release, which decreases water reabsorption and increases water loss to lower blood volume and pressure; and
- 3) It decreases thirst.

Fig 5: Mechanism of action of ANP (Klabunde, 2021).

BLOOD VOLUME AND OSMOLARITY AFFECT THE VOLUME AND COMPOSITION OF URINE

Urine volume and composition reflect hydration levels. For example, if Mr. X consumes insufficient fluids and becomes dehydrated, his body will produce a little volume of concentrated urine as a means of conserving water. The specific gravity of concentrated urine is high. The weight of a substance divided by the weight of an equal amount of water is known as its specific gravity. Water has a specific gravity of 1.000 because equal amounts of water weigh the same at the same temperature.

The specific gravity of normal urine ranges from 1.001 to 1.035 and is determined by the concentration of solutes, including electrolytes. The specific gravity of a solution increases with the concentration of solutes. Mrs. Z, on the other hand, drinks a lot of fluids and is too hydrated. She will discharge a high amount of dilute urine with low specific

gravity, resulting in a lower electrolyte level (Silverthorne, 2013).

ELECTROLYTE BALANCE

- Electrolytes are an important component of bodily fluids. They enter the body via the food and beverages we consume.
- Electrolytes leave the body mostly through the kidneys in the form of urine, but they also exit through the skin and feces.
- Severe vomiting and diarrhea can cause the body to lose both water and electrolytes, resulting in a water and electrolyte imbalance.
- The amounts of electrolytes in human fluids must be kept within narrow limits, and even minor deviations from these limits can have devastating or fatal consequences.

ELECTROLYTE IMBALANCE

Electrolyte abnormalities are commonly found in a variety of disorders. Imbalances in each electrolyte must be examined

in conjunction with one another, and investigations must strive to explain the clinical condition in order to provide effective and successful treatment. The most common electrolyte imbalances are hypo- and hyper-states of sodium, potassium, calcium, and magnesium (Shiber and Mattu, 2002). The body requires an even balance of electrolytes to function effectively. Otherwise, key body systems may be compromised. Severe electrolyte imbalances can lead to significant complications like coma, convulsions, and cardiac arrest.

SODIUM ION (Na⁺)

Roles/Functions of sodium

Sodium is the most abundant cation in the ECF, accounting for over 90% of all extracellular cations (Polancic, 2013). Na⁺ is abundant and plays an important function in water distribution, plasma volume, and osmotic pressure maintenance. Slight variations in plasma Na⁺ concentration will cause significant changes in plasma volume. When Na⁺ is removed from the plasma, plasma volume decreases as extracellular water enters the cells to restore normal plasma osmolality and Na⁺ concentration. In contrast, an increased concentration of Na⁺ in the ECF causes an increase in plasma volume, which reduces elevated plasma osmolality. In addition to maintaining osmotic pressure, Na⁺ maintains acid-base balance and stimulates nerve and muscle cells.

Regulation of sodium

Changes in plasma osmolality and volume caused by differences in Na⁺ concentration set off a cascade of regulatory actions on osmoreceptors and endocrine glands, altering water intake and excretion (Shah *et al.*, 2022). Hyperosmotic conditions or decreased blood volume due to elevated Na⁺ concentration activate hypothalamic osmoreceptors, causing thirst (Koshy and Jamil, 2023). Increased fluid intake increases the water content of the ECF, diluting high Na⁺ levels and lowering plasma osmolality. In the presence of antidiuretic hormone (ADH) or vasopressin, aldosterone, and natriuretic peptides, the kidneys play an important role in Na⁺ control.

Antidiuretic hormone, which is released by the posterior pituitary gland in response to increased plasma osmolality and/or decreased plasma volume, acts on the nephron's distal convoluted tubules (DCT) and collecting ducts to increase renal water resorption, increasing plasma volume and decreasing plasma osmolality (Cuzzo *et al.*, 2023). Pressure sensing systems in the juxtaglomerular apparatus in the nephron's afferent arteriole respond to changes in blood pressure caused by variations in circulating blood volume (Dalal *et al.*, 2023). Lower pressure on the juxtaglomerular apparatus owing to lower ECF volume causes the kidney to release renin, which then stimulates the adrenal cortex to release aldosterone.

Aldosterone, in turn, acts on the DCT, increasing Na⁺ resorption and water retention. When the juxtaglomerular apparatus detects increased pressure, it limits the secretion of renin and aldosterone. Natriuretic peptides increase renal

excretion of water and Na⁺ via reducing resorption in the proximal convoluted tubules (Adam, 2017).

Disorders of sodium

1. Hyponatremia

Hyponatremia, or low plasma Na⁺ concentration, is caused by an increase in Na loss (depletional hyponatremia), or by an increase in water retention or a water imbalance associated to Na⁺ loss (dilutional hyponatremia). Depletional hyponatremia can be caused by renal or non-renal losses (Verbrugge *et al.*, 2015). Renal Na⁺ loss is seen with the use of diuretics that inhibit resorption of Cl⁻ and Na⁺ in the ascending loop of Henle (e.g., thiazides), in patients with hypoaldosteronism (Addison's disease) where Na⁺ is lost to the urine due to a lack of Na⁺ resorption, with salt-wasting nephropathies such as chronic interstitial nephritis and polycystic kidney disease, and in metabolic alkalosis with prolonged vomiting where renal loss of Na⁺ accompanies renal bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) excretion (Bell and Mandalia, 2022).

Non-renal Na⁺ loss can occur through the GI tract (e.g., vomiting and diarrhea) or the skin (e.g., severe burns and trauma). Dilutional hyponatremia occurs when plasma Na⁺ concentrations drop due to an increase in plasma water volume. Dilutional hyponatremia can be caused by excessive water intake, the syndrome of inappropriate ADH (SIADH), in which excess ADH secretion causes increased renal water retention, widespread edema, acute and chronic renal failure, and hyperglycemia (Warren *et al.*, 2023). Patients with widespread edema caused by congestive heart failure, cirrhosis, or nephrotic syndrome may develop dilutional hyponatremia as a result of decreased plasma volume (John and Thuluvath, 2015; Rodriguez *et al.*, 2019). This lower plasma volume induces the release of ADH, which causes renal water retention.

With hyperglycemia, elevated solute concentrations in the ECF cause an extracellular transfer of water from the interior of the cell to the ECF to restore osmotic balance, lowering Na⁺ concentration (Tzamaloukas *et al.*, 2019).

2. Hypernatremia

Hypernatremia, or an elevated Na⁺ concentration, is caused by decreased water intake, excess water loss in comparison to Na⁺ loss, and/or excessive Na⁺ intake or retention. The elderly, those with impaired mental status, and infants are the most vulnerable to hypernatremia because they are unable to rehydrate themselves despite a normal thirst reflex (Shah *et al.*, 2014; Warren *et al.*, 2023). Excess water loss relative to Na⁺ loss is seen with GI tract loss (e.g., vomiting and diarrhoea); excessive sweating without proper fluid replacement (e.g., prolonged fever or exercise); and diabetes insipidus (lack of ADH or lack of response resulting in decreased water resorption and excessive water loss in urine) (Daley and Avva, 2024).

Ingestion of high amounts of Na⁺ salts, or infusion of significant amounts of sodium chloride (NaCl) or sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃), might result in a net rise in Na⁺

concentration relative to water. Excess aldosterone, as observed in hyperaldosteronism, promotes increased Na^+ resorption in the kidneys, resulting in hypernatremia (Kristensen *et al.*, 2022).

Symptoms of Sodium Imbalance

Symptoms of Na^+ imbalance are caused by variations in osmolality rather than a changed plasma Na^+ concentration. Hyponatremia symptoms are induced by cell enlargement as water goes into the ECF and ICF to regulate the osmotic pressure. Hypernatremia symptoms are induced by cell dehydration when water is lost to the extracellular fluid (Sumi *et al.*, 2025).

Symptoms of hyponatremia and hypernatremia are similar, including neurological symptoms such as headache.

Lethargy

Muscle weakness and loss of coordination

mental bewilderment

POTASSIUM ION (K^+)

Role/Function of potassium

Potassium is the body's primary intracellular cation, accounting for 98% of K^+ in the ICF (Mroz, 2007). When a cell is at rest, the ratio of intracellular to extracellular K^+ concentration causes a voltage difference across the cell membrane (resting membrane potential), making K^+ a major determinant of resting membrane potential and necessary for neuromuscular cell excitability (Grider *et al.*, 2023). Changes in resting membrane potential affect the distance between the resting membrane potential and the threshold potential required to initiate an action potential and nerve impulse (Grider *et al.*, 2023). Elevated plasma K^+ concentrations reduce resting membrane potential, resulting in reduced difference between the resting membrane potential and threshold potential. Low plasma K^+ concentrations, on the other hand, raise the resting membrane potential and shift it away from the threshold potential. The ensuing disparity between the cells' resting membrane potential and threshold potential alters cell excitability, resulting in muscular weakness, paralysis, or arrhythmia (Campese and Adenuga, 2016). Potassium also plays an important role in cellular metabolism by regulating protein and glycogen production.

Regulation of potassium

After consuming food, K^+ is absorbed in the GI tract. A small fraction is absorbed by muscle and liver cells, whereas the majority is eliminated by the kidney. The glomerulus filters K^+ , which is almost fully resorbed in the kidneys' proximal convoluted tubules. Under the indirect regulation of aldosterone, K^+ is secreted in urine in exchange for Na^+ in the DCT (Pearce *et al.*, 2022). To maintain high internal K^+ and high external Na^+ concentrations, K^+ is constantly carried into the cell and Na^+ out of the cell against the concentration gradient via the Na-K-ATPase pump in the cell membrane (Enyedi and Czirják, 2010; Chrysafides *et al.*, 2023).

Disorders of potassium

1. Hypokalemia

Hypokalemia is defined as a reduction in plasma K^+ concentration. It can be caused by renal loss, GI tract loss, or enhanced cellular absorption. The most prevalent cause of renal loss-induced hypokalemia is the use of diuretics, which act on the proximal convoluted tubules to increase the flow of filtrate through the tubules, hence increasing K^+ excretion (Bell and Mandalia, 2022). In renal tubular acidosis, potassium excretion in the urine increases to maintain electroneutrality while H^+ excretion decreases. Greater renal K^+ excretion coincides with greater Na^+ resorption in hyperaldosteronism (Alamilla-Sanchez *et al.*, 2025). Hypomagnesemia causes hypokalemia by increasing aldosterone secretion and decreasing the activity of the Na-K-ATPase pump (Ketritz and Loffing, 2023).

Vomiting, diarrhea, gastric suction, malabsorption, and laxative usage can all cause excessive K^+ loss from the GI tract, resulting in hypokalemia. Alkalosis and insulin overdose both cause hypokalemia via a cellular shift of K^+ . In alkalosis, a lack of H^+ in the ECF causes more H^+ to flow from the cell to the ECF and K^+ to enter the cell, resulting in electrical neutrality (Emmett, 2020). Insulin stimulates the entrance of K^+ into skeletal muscle and liver cells (SyLOW *et al.*, 2021).

2. Hyperkalemia

Increased plasma K^+ , often known as hyperkalemia, occurs in situations characterized by decreased renal excretion, altered cellular absorption, enhanced cell lysis, and/or increased consumption. Renal excretion of K^+ is reduced in acute and chronic renal failure, by some diuretics, and in hypoaldosteronism (Ueda *et al.*, 2016). Cellular potassium absorption is changed in the context of diabetes mellitus with insulin insufficiency because hyperglycemia and the resulting hyperosmolar plasma remove water and potassium from the cells (Goia-Nishide *et al.*, 2022). In metabolic acidosis, excess H^+ is buffered within the cells, causing K^+ to depart the cells to maintain electroneutrality (Udensi and Tchounwou, 2017). Digoxin toxicity is related with a cellular shift in K^+ concentration, resulting in hyperkalemia as the Na-K-ATPase pump is blocked (Regina *et al.*, 2025).

Increased cell lysis in muscle cells, as well as white and red blood cells, as a result of intravascular hemolysis, traumatic damage, or tumor lysis syndrome causes K^+ to be released from the intracellular environment (Eleftheriadis *et al.*, 2012). Hyperkalemia in hospitalized patients is most commonly caused by increased intake of K^+ through oral or intravenous replacement medication (Khanagavi *et al.*, 2014). Artificial hyperkalemia, also known as pseudohyperkalemia, is usually caused by sample hemolysis, extended tourniquet use, or extreme fist clenching, as well as the release of K^+ from red blood cells, white blood cells, and platelets during coagulation in vitro (Okpara *et al.*, 2023).

Symptoms of Potassium Imbalance

Symptoms of K⁺ imbalance are directly related to changes in the cells' resting membrane potential, which alters neuromuscular conduction and causes cardiac-conduction abnormalities. Hypokalemia raises the resting membrane potential, decreasing cell excitability and producing muscle weakness, cramps, paralysis, and tachycardia, with the chance of cardiac arrest (Thu Kyaw and Maung, 2022). Although hyperkalemia initially increases cell excitability by decreasing the resting membrane potential, persistent depolarization of the cell membranes induces inactivation of the Na⁺ channels in the cell membrane and, eventually, a decrease in cell excitability (Weiss *et al.*, 2017; Hunter and Bailey, 2019).

Symptoms include muscle weakness, Paralysis, Conduction defects, Respiratory muscle weakness and bradycardia.

Potassium levels more than 10.0 mEq/L (10.0 mmol/L) are almost always related with death from cardiac vascular collapse (Sunheimer and Graves, 2011).

CALCIUM ION (Ca²⁺)

Role/Function of Calcium

Calcium is the fifth-most prevalent element in the body (Weaver and Peacock, 2019)). Calcium plays a variety of vital roles in the body, including bone mineralization, muscular contraction and excitability, blood hemostasis, and plasma membrane stability (Yu and Sharma, 2023). Intracellularly, Ca²⁺ serves as a key second messenger in enzyme activation. Ninety-eight percent of the body's Ca²⁺ is contained as hydroxyapatite crystals in the skeleton, with the remaining in three forms: ionized; linked with anions bicarbonate, lactate, phosphate, or citrate; or bound to plasma proteins (mostly albumin) (Hamroun *et al.*, 2020).

Approximately 50% of plasma Ca²⁺ is ionized, which is the only physiologically active form (Gidenne *et al.*, 2003). Another 10% of plasma Ca a²⁺ is connected with anions, while 40% is bound to proteins (Schindler and Scot, 2015). Ionized Ca²⁺ is a more reliable indicator of Ca²⁺ disorders than total calcium, which is frequently influenced by changes in anions and plasma protein concentrations (Mamedova *et al.*, 2024). As plasma anions and protein concentrations fluctuate due to severe illness or surgery, so does the concentration of bound calcium, and hence the total calcium measurement. However, the levels of ionized Ca²⁺ will not alter.

Regulation of Calcium

Calcium homeostasis is regulated by three regulators: parathyroid hormone (PTH), vitamin D, and calcitonin (Pu *et al.*, 2016; Brown, 1999; Mundy and Guise, 1999). In reaction to low ionized Ca²⁺ levels in the plasma, the parathyroid gland secretes thyroid hormone. When ionized Ca²⁺ levels are low, PTH stimulates bone resorption by activating osteoclastic cells, which break down hydroxyapatite crystals and release Ca²⁺ into the plasma (Ciosek *et al.*, 2021; Crooks and Bendall, 2021). Parathyroid hormone also acts on the kidneys, enhancing Ca²⁺ resorption in the renal tubules and stimulating the generation of vitamin D's active form, 1,25-(OH)₂D₃ (Voltan *et al.*, 2023). This type of vitamin D promotes Ca²⁺ absorption in the gut and kidneys while also stimulating bone resorption.

Calcitonin, secreted by the thyroid gland's parafollicular cells, is released in response to high Ca²⁺ concentrations to counterbalance the effects of PTH and vitamin D by suppressing bone osteoclastic activity and kidney Ca²⁺ resorption (Babić Leko *et al.*, 2022; Levine *et al.*, 2014).

Fig. 7: Parathyroid hormone regulation of calcium level (Haslett *et al.*, 2002), as referenced by Manitshana, (2020).

Disorders of Calcium

1. Hypocalcemia

Chronic renal failure commonly causes hypocalcemia due to decreased production of 1,25-(OH)₂D₃ and hyperphosphatemia, as PO₄ binds and reduces Ca²⁺ (Raju and Saxena, 2025; Hryciuk *et al.*, 2023). Magnesium shortage promotes vitamin D resistance by inhibiting PTH secretion and impairing its effect, resulting in hypocalcemia (Fiorentini *et al.*, 2021; Fong and Khan, 2012). In primary hypoparathyroidism, reduced PTH excretion causes increased Ca²⁺ excretion in the kidneys and improper vitamin D metabolism (Sell *et al.*, 2022; Pasięka *et al.*, 2022). Although uncommon, pseudohypoparathyroidism is a genetic condition that causes Ca²⁺ loss in urine due to organ resistance to PTH in the context of adequate PTH secretion (Mantovani *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, vitamin D insufficiency and severe pancreatitis lead to lower Ca²⁺ levels (Siuka *et al.*, 2025; Cai *et al.*, 2022; Huh *et al.*, 2019). Chronic disease-related hypoalbuminemia is the most common cause of low total Ca²⁺ concentrations. While total calcium levels are reduced due to albumin insufficiency, ionized Ca²⁺ levels remain normal, demonstrating the need of measuring ionized Ca²⁺ levels in critically ill patients (Fernandes and Pereira, 2024; Kenny *et al.*, 2021).

2. Hypercalcemia

Primary hyperparathyroidism is the leading cause of hypercalcemia, with cancer a close second (Mirrakhimov, 2015). Cancer-related hypercalcemia is caused by tumors that produce parathyroid hormone-related protein (PTHrP), which are associated with squamous cell lung malignancies and other epithelial cell carcinomas (Bartkiewicz *et al.*, 2024; Mirrakhimov, 2015). PTHrP interacts to PTH receptors, releasing Ca²⁺ from bone while blocking Ca²⁺ excretion in the kidneys. Immobilization and bone metastases, as observed in malignant melanoma, breast cancer, and lymphoma, will raise plasma Ca²⁺ levels by driving bone resorption. Hypercalcemia can also be caused by vitamin D overdose, thiazide diuretics, renal failure, or hyperthyroidism.

Symptoms of Calcium Imbalance

Owing to the role of Ca²⁺ in neuromuscular activity, Ca²⁺ imbalances often manifest as neuromuscular symptoms.

Symptoms of hypocalcemia are the result of increased excitability of neuromuscular function and include; tetany, Muscle cramps, Paresthesia, Seizures, Confusion, Hallucinations and Cardiac arrhythmias.

When Ca²⁺ concentrations are elevated (hypercalcemia), decreased activity in nerve and muscle cells can result in: weakness, anorexia, lethargy, confusion, impaired concentration and changes in cardiac function. Hypercalcemia is also associated with deposition of calcium in soft tissues of the kidney, joints, and cornea.

MAGNESIUM ION (Mg²⁺)

Role/Function of magnesium

Magnesium is the second most prevalent intracellular cation. The majority of the body's Mg²⁺ is located in bone, with

plasma accounting for only around 1% (Sunheimer and Graves, 2011). Magnesium serves as a cofactor for over 300 enzymes required for regular bodily function (National Institutes of Health, 2022). It is essential for neuromuscular transmission and the synthesis of proteins, nucleic acids, carbohydrates, and lipids. It is necessary for ion transport and modulates intracellular potassium mobility.

Regulation of Magnesium

Although bone reserves contain the majority of the body's Mg²⁺, they do not quickly release Mg²⁺ into the bloodstream. Mg²⁺ is regulated in the kidneys, where variations in intake are balanced by changes in urine resorption, which are influenced by plasma Mg²⁺ concentrations, plasma Ca²⁺ concentrations, acid-base state, and many hormones (Dutta and Layton, 2024). The renal threshold for Mg²⁺ is very close to the normal plasma concentration; thus, even minor increases in plasma Mg²⁺ might cause increased kidney excretion (Adomako and Yu, 2024; Swaminathan, 2003). In deficient situations, Mg²⁺ is easily absorbed through the Henle and DCT loops (Curry and Yu, 2018). Mg²⁺ transport is influenced by increased plasma Ca²⁺ concentrations, metabolic acidosis, and hypokalemia, all of which limit Mg²⁺ resorption in the Henle loop. Several hormones affect Mg²⁺ resorption in the kidneys, however unlike Na⁺, K⁺, and Ca²⁺, no hormones are related with Mg²⁺ homeostasis (Blaine *et al.*, 2015).

Disorders of Magnesium

1. Hypomagnesemia

Hypomagnesemia is most commonly observed in hospitalized patients (Al Shukri *et al.*, 2023). The primary causes of hypomagnesemia are lower intake, GI tract loss, and renal loss. Intestinal loss can result from severe diarrhea, malabsorption diseases, nasogastric suctioning, pancreatitis, laxative usage, and gastrointestinal bypass surgery. Renal tubular diseases, metabolic acidosis, hypercalcemia, hyperaldosteronism, hyperparathyroidism, and medicines such as diuretics, cyclosporine, and aminoglycosides all contribute to increased Mg²⁺ excretion in the urine.

2. Hypermagnesemia

Although less common than hypomagnesemia, hypermagnesemia is frequently associated with renal failure and Mg²⁺ poisoning (Aal-Hamad *et al.*, 2023; Qazi *et al.*, 2021). Because the kidneys are the primary regulators of Mg²⁺ homeostasis, plasma levels of Mg²⁺ rise when renal function declines and Mg²⁺ excretion is compromised. People with renal failure who also take magnesium-containing drugs (such as antacids, enemas, or laxatives) are at the highest risk of developing hypermagnesemia. Hypoaldosteronism, hypothyroidism, and hypopituitarism are all associated with decreased renal Mg²⁺ excretion (Karaca and Kelestimur, 2025). Hypermagnesemia can arise as a result of therapeutic intravenous magnesium therapy in pre-eclampsia or eclampsia, which is used to enhance uterine blood flow and reduce uterine contractions (Marin *et al.*, 2023).

Symptoms of Magnesium Imbalance

Symptoms of a Mg^{2+} imbalance include neuromuscular dysfunction, cardiovascular dysfunction, and anomalies in Ca^{2+} metabolism. Neuromuscular dysfunctions related to the role of Mg^{2+} in the control of acetylcholine at the neuromuscular junction are demonstrated by hypomagnesemia, which causes enhanced neuromuscular excitability, whereas hypermagnesemia depresses the neuromuscular system (Al Alawi *et al.*, 2018; Souza *et al.*, 2023). Changes in Mg^{2+} concentration also disrupt the balance of other essential electrolytes (K^+ and Ca^{2+}), resulting in an alteration in Na-K-ATPase pump activity and a subsequent change in resting membrane potential, causing cardiovascular malfunction and electrocardiogram changes (Dhalla *et al.*, 2024). Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} regulation is intimately linked, therefore anomalies in Ca^{2+} metabolism is related with Mg^{2+} imbalances. Patients with low Mg^{2+} levels may have tetany, convulsions, cramping, paralysis, agitation, or psychosis. Patients with high Mg^{2+} concentrations experience respiratory center depression, hypotension, involuntary muscular paralysis, lethargy, and bradycardia (Den and Meinders, 2005).

CHLORIDE ION (Cl^-)

Chloride is the most abundant extracellular anion. Chloride contributes significantly to the osmotic pressure difference between the ICF and ECF and is essential for maintaining appropriate hydration. Chloride balances cations in the ECF,

ensuring that the fluid remains electrically neutral. In the renal system, chloride ion secretion and reabsorption follow the same pathways as sodium ions.

Disorders of Chloride Ion

1. Hypochloremia

Hypochloremia, or low blood chloride levels, can occur due to impaired renal tubular absorption. Vomiting, diarrhea, and metabolic acidosis can all cause hypochloremia.

2. Hyperchloremia

Hyperchloremia, or elevated blood chloride levels, can be caused by dehydration, an excessive intake of food salt (NaCl) or seawater, aspirin overdose, congestive heart failure, and cystic fibrosis, a congenital chronic lung condition. In persons with cystic fibrosis, chloride levels in sweat are two to five times higher than normal levels, and sweat analysis is frequently used to diagnose the disease.

BICARBONATE ION (HCO_3^-)

Bicarbonate is the second most common anion in the bloodstream. Its primary job is to maintain your body's acid-base balance as part of buffer systems. Bicarbonate ions are the outcome of a chemical reaction that begins with carbon dioxide (CO_2) and water, both of which are created at the end of aerobic metabolism. Only a little amount of CO_2 can dissolve in bodily fluids. Thus, more than 90% of CO_2 is transformed into bicarbonate ions, HCO_3^- , by the following reactions

The bidirectional arrows show that the reactions can proceed in either way, depending on the concentrations of the reactants and products. Carbon dioxide is produced in significant quantities in tissues with high metabolic rates. Carbon dioxide is converted to bicarbonate in the cytoplasm of red blood cells by an enzyme called carbonic anhydrase. Bicarbonate is carried by the blood. Once in the lungs, the events reverse, with CO_2 being produced from bicarbonate and expelled as metabolic waste.

SOME DISEASES ASSOCIATED WITH ELECTROLYTE DISORDER

- Kidney disease
- Congestive heart failure
- Cancer
- Diabetic ketoacidosis
- Thyroid and parathyroid tumours
- Paget's disease

CAUSES OF ELECTROLYTE DISORDERS

Electrolyte disorders are most often caused by a loss of bodily fluids through prolonged vomiting, diarrhea, or sweating. They may also develop due to fluid loss related to burns. Certain medications can cause electrolyte disorders as well. In some cases, underlying diseases, such as acute or chronic kidney disease, are to blame. The exact cause may vary depending on the specific type of electrolyte disorder.

COMMON SYMPTOMS OF ELECTROLYTE DISORDER

Mild electrolyte abnormalities may not present any symptoms. Such abnormalities may go unnoticed until they are discovered during a regular blood test. Symptoms typically arise as a disorder progresses to a more severe stage. Although not all electrolyte imbalances elicit the same symptoms, many of them are comparable.

Common symptoms of an electrolyte problem are:

- An irregular heartbeat, rapid heart rate, fatigue, lethargy,
- Convulsions or seizures, nausea and vomiting, Diarrhea or Constipation etc.

RISK FACTORS THAT CAN PREDISPOSE ONE TO HAVING ELECTROLYTE DISORDERS

Anyone can get an electrolyte problem. Certain individuals are at a higher risk due to their medical history. The following conditions enhance your risk of developing an electrolyte disorder:

Alcohol Use Disorder, Cirrhosis, Congestive Heart Failure, Kidney disease, eating disorders including anorexia and bulimia, Trauma, such as serious burns or shattered bones, Thyroid diseases, Adrenal gland diseases, etc.

LABORATORY INVESTIGATION OF ELECTROLYTE DISORDER

Electrolyte panels are tests that employ blood (serum) or urine to evaluate the amounts of electrolytes and CO₂ in the blood. The ion selective electrode (ISE) is an analytical technique for determining ion activity in aqueous solution by detecting the electrical potential. ISE has numerous advantages over other approaches, including:

1. It is relatively affordable and simple to use.
2. It has a large concentration measurement range.
3. Since it measures activity rather than concentration, it is very valuable in biological/medical applications.
4. It is a real-time measurement, which means it can track the change of ion activity over time.
5. It can identify positively and negatively charged ions.

LIMITATIONS OF ION SELECTIVE ELECTRODE

1. The selective ion membrane only enables measured ions to pass, hence the potential is dictated by this specific ion. However, there is no such membrane that only allows for the passage of one ion, hence there are times when many ions can flow through the membrane. As a result, the measured potential is influenced by the passage of "unwanted" ions.
2. Furthermore, because it is dependent on an ion selective membrane, each ISE can only handle one ion, which can be difficult at times.
3. Another issue to consider is that the ion selective electrode measures the concentration of ions in equilibrium on the membrane surface. This does not matter much if the solution is dilute, but at greater concentrations, inter-ionic interactions between the ions in the solution tend to reduce ion mobility, resulting in a lower concentration near the membrane than in the bulk (Scholz, 2010).

Clinical relevance

Sodium levels are used to diagnose and treat aldosteronism (excessive secretion of the hormone aldosterone), diabetes insipidus (chronic excretion of large amounts of dilute urine accompanied by extreme thirst), adrenal hypertension, Addison's disease (caused by adrenal gland destruction), dehydration, inappropriate anti-diuretic hormone secretion, and other electrolyte imbalance diseases. Potassium measurements are used to monitor electrolyte balance in the diagnosis and treatment of diseases defined by low or high blood potassium concentrations.

Chloride measurements aid in the diagnosis and treatment of electrolyte and metabolic problems such as cystic fibrosis and diabetic acidosis. The urinary electrolytes sodium, potassium, and chloride are mostly employed as nutritional markers in healthy people. They are rarely measured in clinical settings, and when they are, it is typically in intensive/critical care units. Their measured values are not diagnostic of any disease in and of themselves; rather, they can be utilized in certain particular scenarios to aid in the diagnosis of a number of rather uncommon clinical disorders. The most important application of urine electrolyte data is in public health studies. Urine salt levels are an important indicator for dietary sodium consumption.

Test principle

An Ion-Selective Electrode (ISE) uses the unique features of specific membrane materials to generate an electrical potential (electromotive force, EMF) for measuring ions in solution. The complete measuring system for a specific ion consists of the ISE, a reference electrode, and electronic circuits that measure and process the EMF to determine the test ion concentration. The Hitachi ISE Module(s) employ a liquid/liquid junction ISE. The sodium and potassium electrodes are neutral carriers, but the chloride electrode is an ion exchanger (Wu, 2006).

Sample collection and use

Serum without hemolysis or significant lipemia is collected using the conventional venipuncture procedure. Only lithium heparin or a plain container can be used. Serum should not remain on the cells after centrifugation. Potassium from the red cells diffuses into the serum, producing artificially high results. Urine should be collected without preservatives and kept refrigerated during collection (Kaplan *et al.*, 2003). Frozen samples are stored at -70°C. When removed from erythrocytes and stored tightly sealed at 2-8°C, the chloride content remains steady for several days. Sodium and potassium are stable for two weeks at 1525°C, or 2-8°C (Young, 1997).

TREATMENT

Treatment differs according on the type of electrolyte problem and the underlying cause. In general, specific treatments are employed to restore the right mineral balance in the body. This includes:

INTRAVENOUS (IV) FLUIDS

Intravenous (IV) fluids, usually sodium chloride, can assist the body rehydrate. This is widely used in cases of dehydration caused by vomiting or diarrhea. Electrolyte supplements can be mixed into IV fluids to remedy deficits.

CERTAIN IV MEDICATIONS

IV medicines can help the body swiftly regain electrolyte balance. They can also prevent against side effects while being treated with another therapy. The medication you receive will be determined by your electrolyte imbalance.

Calcium gluconate, magnesium chloride, and potassium chloride are all medications that could be provided.

Oral medications and supplements

Oral medicines and supplements are frequently used to treat chronic mineral imbalances in the body. This is more prevalent if one has been diagnosed with chronic renal disease.

Medications or supplements for electrolyte disorders may include calcium (gluconate, carbonate, citrate, or lactate), magnesium oxide, potassium chloride, phosphate binders like sevelamer hydrochloride (Renagel), lanthanum (Fosrenol), and calcium carbonate.

CONCLUSION

Water, which is a major component of human fluids, is the most prevalent substance in the body. Water is essential for a variety of physiological activities, including digestion, nutrition absorption and utilization, distribution, waste excretion, perfusion, and hemodynamic maintenance. Fluid and electrolyte homeostasis happens through various mechanisms that ensure correct functioning. Electrolytes are substances dissolved in bodily fluids. The distribution has a significant impact on the overall fluid balance. Sodium chloride is primarily present in extracellular fluid, whereas potassium and phosphate are the most common ions in intracellular fluid. Electrolytes have several important roles in the body. Homeostasis of Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+} is required for fluid balance, neuron and muscle excitation, enzyme activity, acid-base balance, and electroneutrality. Electrolyte imbalances are connected with changes in distribution and regulation mechanisms. Imbalances in electrolyte concentrations affect the distribution of linked electrolytes throughout the body's fluid compartments and exhibit themselves in comparable ways, necessitating the evaluation of electrolytes as a group rather than separately.

REFERENCES

1. Aal-Hamad, A.H., Al-Alawi, A.M., Kashoub, M.S., & Falhammar, H. (2023). Hypermagnesemia in Clinical Practice. *Medicina (Kaunas, Lithuania)*, 59(7), 1190. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina59071190>
2. Adam, F. (2017). Everything you need to know about electrolytes. *Medical News Today*, 1-10.
3. Adomako, E.A., & Yu, A.S.L. (2024). Magnesium Disorders: Core Curriculum 2024. *American Journal of Kidney Disease*, 83(6), 803-815. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.ajkd.2023.10.017>
4. Al Alawi, A.M., Majoni, S.W., & Falhammar, H. (2018). Magnesium and Human Health: Perspectives and Research Directions. *International Journal of Endocrinology*, 2018, 9041694. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/9041694>
5. Al Shukri, Z., Al-Maqbali, J.S., Al Alawi, A.M., Al Riyami, N., Al Riyami, S., Al Alawi, H., Al Farai, Q., & Falhammar, H. (2023). Incidence of Dymagnesemia among Medically Hospitalized Patients and Associated Clinical Characteristics: A Prospective Cohort Study, *International Journal of Endocrinology*, 2023, 6650620. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/6650620>
6. Alamilla-Sanchez, M., Alcalá Salgado, M. A., Ulloa Galván, V. M., Yanez Salguero, V., Yamá Estrella, M. B., Morales López, E. F., Ramos García, N. A., Carbajal Zárate, M. O., Salazar Hurtado, J. D., Delgado Pineda, D. A., López González, L., & Flores Garnica, J. M. (2025). Understanding Renal Tubular Function: Key Mechanisms, Clinical Relevance, and Comprehensive Urine Assessment. *Pathophysiology*, 32(3), 33. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathophysiology32030033>
7. Babić Leko, M., Pleić, N., Gunjača, I., & Zemunik, T. (2022). Environmental Factors That Affect Parathyroid Hormone and Calcitonin Levels. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(1), 44. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23010044>
8. Bartkiewicz, P., Kunachowicz, D., Filipski, M., Stebel, A., Ligoda, J., & Rembiałkowska, N. (2024). Hypercalcemia in Cancer: Causes, Effects, and Treatment Strategies. *Cells*, 13(12), 1051. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells13121051>
9. Bell, R., & Mandalia, R. (2022). Diuretics and the kidney. *BJA Education*, 22(6), 216–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjae.2022.02.003>
10. Blackmer, A.B. (2018). Fluids and Electrolytes. In: *PedSAP 2018 Book 2: Fluids, Electrolytes, and Nutrition*, Pp. 7-26. https://www.accp.com/docs/bookstore/pedsap/ped2018b2_sample.pdf
11. Blaine, J., Chonchol, M., & Levi, M. (2015). Renal control of calcium, phosphate, and magnesium homeostasis. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology: CJASN*, 10(7), 1257–1272. <https://doi.org/10.2215/CJN.09750913>
12. Brinkman, J.E., Dorius, B., & Sharma, S. (2023). Physiology, Body Fluids. In: *StatPearls [Internet]*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK482447/>
13. Brown, E.M. (1999). Physiology and pathophysiology of the extracellular calcium sensing receptor. *American Journal of Medicine*, 106(2), 238-53. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9343\(98\)00418-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9343(98)00418-5)
14. Burnell, T., & Turner, B. (2025). Hypertension. <https://simplemed.co.uk/subjects/cardiovascular/hypertension>
15. Cai, F., Hu, C., Chen, C. J., Han, Y. P., Lin, Z. Q., Deng, L. H., & Xia, Q. (2022). Vitamin D and Pancreatitis: A Narrative Review of Current

- Evidence. *Nutrients*, 14(10), 2113. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14102113>
16. Campese, V.M., & Adenuga, G. (2016). Electrophysiological and clinical consequences of hyperkalemia. *Kidney International Supplements*, 6(1), 16–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.kisu.2016.01.003>
 17. Chrysafides, S.M., Bordes, S.J., & Sharma, S. (2023). Physiology, Resting Potential. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK538338/>
 18. Ciosek, Z., Kot, K., Kosik-Bogacka, D., Łanocha-Arendarczyk, N., & Rotter, I. (2021). The Effects of Calcium, Magnesium, Phosphorus, Fluoride, and Lead on Bone Tissue. *Biomolecules*, 11(4), 506. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom11040506>
 19. Crooks, M., & Bendall, S. (2021). Parathyroid hormone and vitamin D: from bench to bedside. *Orthopaedics and Trauma*, 32(5), 267–273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmorth.2021.07.002>
 20. Curry F.R. (2005). Atrial natriuretic peptide: an essential physiological regulator of transvascular fluid, protein transport, and plasma volume. *The Journal of Clinical Investigation*, 115(6), 1458–1461. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI25417>
 21. Curry, J.N., & Yu, A.S.L. (2018). Magnesium Handling in the Kidney. *Advances in Chronic Kidney Disease*, 25(3), 236–243. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.ackd.2018.01.003>
 22. Cuzzo, B., Padala, S.A., & Lappin, S.L. (2023). Physiology, Vasopressin. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK526069/>
 23. Dalal, R., Bruss, Z.S., & Sehdev, J.S. (2023). Physiology, Renal Blood Flow and Filtration. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK482248/>
 24. Daley, S.F., & Avva, U. (2024). Pediatric Dehydration. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK436022/>
 25. Den, O. D.T., & Meinders, A.E. (2005). Vasopressin: physiology and clinical use in patients with vasodilatory shock: a review. *The Netherlands Journal of Medicine*, 63, 4–13.
 26. Dhalla, N.S., Elimban, V., & Adameova, A.D. (2024). Role of Na⁺-K⁺ ATPase Alterations in the Development of Heart Failure. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 25(19), 10807. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms251910807>
 27. Dunne, C. (2023). Electrolytes: Mechanisms and implications for internal body Functioning. *Clinical Nutrition and Hospital Dietetics*, 43(3), 01–02. <https://doi.org/10.12873/0211-6057.43.03.206>
 28. Dutta, P., & Layton, A. T. (2024). Modeling calcium and magnesium balance: Regulation by calciotropic hormones and adaptations under varying dietary intake. *iScience*, 27(11), 111077. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2024.111077>
 29. Eleftheriadis, T., Leivaditis, K., Antoniadi, G., & Liakopoulos, V. (2012). Differential diagnosis of hyperkalemia: an update to a complex problem. *Hippokratia*, 16(4), 294–302.
 30. Emmett, M. (2020). Metabolic Alkalosis: A Brief Pathophysiologic Review. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology: CJASN*, 15(12), 1848–1856. <https://doi.org/10.2215/CJN.16041219>
 31. Enyedi, P., & Czirják, G. (2010). Molecular background of leak K⁺ currents: two-pore domain potassium channels. *Physiological Reviews*, 90(2), 559–605. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00029.2009>
 32. Essa, A., & Macnab, R. (2021). Regulation of fluid and electrolyte balance. *Anaesthesia and Intensive Care Medicine*, 22(7), 428–433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mpaic.2021.05.013>
 33. Fernandes, C., & Pereira, L. (2024). Hypocalcemia in critical care settings, from its clinical relevance to its treatment: A narrative review. *Anaesthesia Critical Care and Pain Medicine*, 43(6), 101438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.accpm.2024.101438>
 34. Fiorentini, D., Cappadone, C., Farruggia, G., & Prata, C. (2021). Magnesium: Biochemistry, Nutrition, Detection, and Social Impact of Diseases Linked to Its Deficiency. *Nutrients*, 13(4), 1136. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13041136>
 35. Fong, J., & Khan, A. (2012). Hypocalcemia: updates in diagnosis and management for primary care. *Canadian Family Physician Medecin de famille canadien*, 58(2), 158–162.
 36. Germann, W.J., & Stanfield, C.L. (2016). Principles of Human Physiology. San Francisco, CA: Pearson Education.
 37. Gidenne, S., Vigezzi, J.F., Delacour, H., Damiano, J., & Clerc, Y. (2003). Dosage direct du calcium ionisé plasmatique ou estimation par calcul: intérêts et limites [Direct determination or estimated value of plasma ionized calcium: indications and limits]. *Annales de biologie clinique*, 61(4), 393–399.
 38. Goia-Nishide, K., Coregliano-Ring, L., & Rangel, É. B. (2022). Hyperkalemia in Diabetes Mellitus Setting. *Diseases (Basel, Switzerland)*, 10(2), 20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diseases10020020>
 39. Grider, M.H., Jessu, R., & Kabir, R. (2023). Physiology, Action Potential. In: StatPearls

- [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK538143/>
40. Hamroun, A., Pekar, J.D., Lionet, A., Ghulam, A., Maboudou, P., Mercier, A., Brousseau, T., Grzych, G., Glowacki, F. (2020). Ionized calcium: analytical challenges and clinical relevance. *Journal of Laboratory and Precision Medicine*, 5, 22. <https://doi.org/10.21037/jlpm-20-60>
 41. Haslett, C., Boon, N., & Colledge, N. (2002). Davidson's principles and practice of medicine. 19th ed. Edinburgh, United Kingdom: Churchill Livingstone, p. 714-716.
 42. Hryciuk, M., Heleniak, Z., & Dębska-Ślizień, A. (2023). Management of chronic kidney disease — mineral and bone disorder. *Renal Disease and Transplantation Forum*, 16(3), 65-80. <https://doi.org/10.5603/rdtf.96819>
 43. Huh, J. H., Kim, J. W., & Lee, K. J. (2019). Vitamin D deficiency predicts severe acute pancreatitis. *United European Gastroenterology Journal*, 7(1), 90–95. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2050640618811489>
 44. Hunter, R.W., & Bailey, M.A. (2019). Hyperkalemia: pathophysiology, risk factors and consequences. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*, 34(Supplement 3), iii2–iii11, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ndt/gfz206>
 45. Internet lectures. (2011). Water and the major ions. <https://funaab.edu.ng/funaab-ocw/LectureByWeek/LectureByWeek/VBB%20201/Lecture%2011.pdf>
 46. Jain A. (2015). Body fluid composition. *Pediatrics in Review*, 36(4), 141–152. <https://doi.org/10.1542/pir.36-4-141>
 47. John, S., & Thuluvath, P.J. (2015). Hyponatremia in cirrhosis: pathophysiology and management. *World Journal of Gastroenterology*, 21(11), 3197–3205. <https://doi.org/10.3748/wjg.v21.i11.3197>
 48. Kaplan, L. A., Pesce, A. J., & Kazmierczak, S. C. (2003). Clinical Chemistry: Theory, Analysis, Correlation (4th ed.). St. Louis, Missouri, MO: Mosby
 49. Karaca, Z., & Kelestimur, F. (2025). Sheehan syndrome: a current approach to a dormant disease. *Pituitary*, 28(1), 20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11102-024-01481-1>
 50. Kenny, C.M., Murphy, C.E., Boyce, D.S., Ashley, D.M., & Jahanmir, J. (2021). Things We Do for No Reason™: Calculating a "Corrected Calcium" Level. *Journal of Hospital Medicine*, 16(8), 499–501. <https://doi.org/10.12788/jhm.3619>
 51. Kettritz, R., & Loffing, J. Potassium homeostasis – Physiology and pharmacology in a clinical context. *Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 249, 108489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pharmthera.2023.108489>
 52. Khanagavi, J., Gupta, T., Aronow, W. S., Shah, T., Garg, J., Ahn, C., Sule, S., & Peterson, S. (2014). Hyperkalemia among hospitalized patients and association between duration of hyperkalemia and outcomes. *Archives of Medical Science: AMS*, 10(2), 251–257. <https://doi.org/10.5114/aoms.2014.42577>
 53. Klabunde, R.E. (2021). Natriuretic peptide formation and release. In: Cardiovascular Physiology Concepts, 3rd edition textbook, Published by Wolters Kluwer. <https://cvphysiology.com/blood-pressure/bp017>
 54. Klabunde, R.E. (2021). Vasopressin (Antidiuretic Hormone). In: Cardiovascular Physiology Concepts, 3rd edition textbook, Published by Wolters Kluwer. <https://cvphysiology.com/blood-pressure/bp016>
 55. Koshy, R.M., & Jamil, R.T. (2023). Physiology, Osmoreceptors. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK557510/>
 56. Kristensen, M., Fenton, R.A., & Poulsen, S.B. (2022). Dissecting the Effects of Aldosterone and Hypokalemia on the Epithelial Na⁺ Channel and the NaCl Cotransporter. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2022.800055>
 57. Levine, B.S., Rodriguez, M., & Felsenfeld, A.J. (2014). Serum calcium and bone: effect of PTH, phosphate, vitamin D and uremia. *Nefrologia*, 34(5), 545-692. <https://doi.org/10.3265/Nefrologia.pre2014.Jun.12379>
 58. Maher, W., & Macnab, R. (2018). Regulation of fluid and electrolyte balance. *Anaesthesia and Intensive Care Medicine*, 19(5), 245-248. <https://doi.org/j.mpaic.2018.02.012>
 59. Mamedova E.O., Golounina O.O., & Belaya Z.E. (2024). Albumin adjustment of total serum calcium – is it worth doing? *Problems of Endocrinology*, 70(6), 45-61. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.14341/probl13503>
 60. Manitshana, N. (2020). Calcium homeostasis. *Southern African Journal of Anaesthesia and Analgesia*, 26(6 Suppl 3), S104-107. <https://doi.org/10.36303/SAJAA.2020.26.6.S3.2551>
 61. Mantovani, G., Bastepe, M., Monk, D., de Sanctis, L., Thiele, S., Usardi, A., Ahmed, S.F., Bufo, R., Choplin, T., De Filippo, G., Devernois, G., Eggermann, T., Elli, F.M., Freson, K., Ramirez, A.G., Germain-Lee, E.L., Groussin, L., Hamdy, N., Hanna, P., Hiort, O., Juppner, H., Kamenicky, P., Knight, N., Kottler, M-L., Norcy, E.L., Lecumberri, B., Levine, M.A., Makitie, O., Martin, R., Martos-Moreno, G.A., Minagawa, M., Murray, P., Pereda,

- A., Pignolo, R., Rejnmark, L., Rodado, R., Rothenbuhler, A., Saraff, V., Shoemaker, A.H., Shore, E.M., Silve, C., Turan, S., Woods, P., Zillikens, M.C., Perez de Nanclares, G., & Linglart, A. (2018). Diagnosis and management of pseudohypoparathyroidism and related disorders: first international Consensus Statement. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*, 14, 476–500 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41574-018-0042-0>
62. Marin, R., Rojas, D., Chiarello, D.I., Rangel, H., Teppa-Garran, A., Fernandez, M., & Ruelle, F. (2023). Magnesium salts in pregnancy. *Journal of Trace Elements and Minerals*, 4, 100071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemin.2023.100071>
63. Martini, F.H., Nath, J.L., & Bartholomew, E.F. (2015). *Fundamentals of Anatomy and Physiology*. Boston, MA: Pearson Education.
64. Meyers R. S. (2009). Pediatric fluid and electrolyte therapy. *The Journal of Pediatric Pharmacology and Therapeutics: JPPT: the official journal of PPAG*, 14(4), 204–211. <https://doi.org/10.5863/1551-6776-14.4.204>
65. Mirrakhimov A.E. (2015). Hypercalcemia of Malignancy: An Update on Pathogenesis and Management. *North American Journal of Medical Sciences*, 7(11), 483–493. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1947-2714.170600>
66. Mirrakhimov A.E. (2015). Hypercalcemia of Malignancy: An Update on Pathogenesis and Management. *North American Journal of Medical Sciences*, 7(11), 483–493. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1947-2714.170600>
67. Mroz, R.C. (2007). Electrolytes. In: Anderson SC, Cockayne S, eds. *Clinical Chemistry Concepts and Applications*. Revised ed. Long Grove, IL: Waveland Press, Pp. 401–419.
68. Mundy, G.R., & Guise, T.A. (1999). Hormonal control of calcium homeostasis. *Clinical Chemistry*, 45(8), 1347–1352. <https://doi.org/10.1093/clinchem/45.8.1347>
69. Nakagawa, Y., Nishikimi, T., & Kuwahara, K. (2019). Atrial and brain natriuretic peptides: Hormones secreted from the heart. *Peptides*, 111, 18–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peptides.2018.05.012>
70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peptides.2018.05.012>
71. National Institutes of Health. (2022). Magnesium: Fact Sheet for Health Professionals. <https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/Magnesium-HealthProfessional/>
72. O'Brien, F., & Walker, I. A. (2014). Fluid homeostasis in the neonate. *Paediatric Anaesthesia*, 24(1), 49–59. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pan.12326>
73. Okpara, H.C., Izuchukwu, E.C.O., & Ilechukwu, E.C. (2023). Pseudohyperkalemia Revisited: An Updated Review of a Foremost Preanalytical Error of Serum or Plasma Potassium Measurement in the Clinical Laboratory. *Nigerian Journal of Medicine*, 32(6), 567–579. https://doi.org/10.4103/NJM.NJM_49_23
74. Open Resources for Nursing (Open RN); Ernstmeyer K, Christman E, editors. *Nursing Fundamentals* [Internet]. Eau Claire (WI): Chippewa Valley Technical College; 2021. Chapter 15 Fluids and Electrolytes. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK591820/>
75. Pasieka, J.L., Wentworth, K., Yeo, C.T., Cremers, S., Dempster, D., Fukumoto, S., Goswami, R., Houillier, P., Levine, M.A., Pasternak, J.D., Perrier, N.D., Sitges-Serra, A., Shoback, D.M. (2022). Etiology and Pathophysiology of Hypoparathyroidism: A Narrative Review. *Journal of Bone and Mineral Research*, 37(12), 2586–2601, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbmr.4714>
76. Pearce, D., Manis, A. D., Nesterov, V., & Korbmacher, C. (2022). Regulation of distal tubule sodium transport: mechanisms and roles in homeostasis and pathophysiology. *Pflugers Archiv: European Journal of Physiology*, 474(8), 869–884. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00424-022-02732-5>
77. Polancic, J.E. (2013). Electrolytes. In: Bishop, M.L., Fody, E.P., Schoeff, L.E., eds. *Clinical Chemistry Principles, Techniques, and Correlations*. 8th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
78. Pu, F., Chen, N., Xue, S. (2016). Calcium intake, calcium homeostasis and health. *Food Science and Human Wellness*, 5(1), 8–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fshw.2016.01.001>
79. Qazi, M., Qazi, H., Nakhoul, G., Provenzano, L.F. (2021). Causes of Hypermagnesaemia: A Literature Review. *European Medical Journal of Nephrology*, 9(1), 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.33590/emjnephrol/21-00033>
80. Raju, S., & Saxena, R. (2025). Hyperphosphatemia in Kidney Failure: Pathophysiology, Challenges, and Critical Role of Phosphorus Management. *Nutrients*, 17(9), 1587. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu17091587>
81. Regina, A.C., Rehman, R., Hai, O. (2025). Cardiac Glycoside and Digoxin Toxicity. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK459165/>
82. Rodriguez, M., Hernandez, M., Cheungpasitporn, W., Kashani, K. B., Riaz, I., Rangaswami, J., Herzog, E., Guglin, M., & Krittanawong, C. (2019). Hyponatremia in Heart Failure: Pathogenesis and Management. *Current cardiology reviews*, 15(4), 252–261.

- <https://doi.org/10.2174/1573403X15666190306111812>
83. Schindler, E.I., & Scott, M.G. (2015). Physiology and disorders of water, electrolyte, and acid-base metabolism. In: Burtis CA, Bruns DE, eds. *Tietz Fundamentals of Clinical Chemistry*. 7th ed. St Louis, MO: Saunders, 681-699.
 84. Schmidt, G.L. (2010). Fluids and electrolytes. In: Corkins M, ed. *The ASPEN Pediatric Nutrition Support Core Curriculum*. Silver Spring, MD. *American Society for Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition*, 2010, 87-102.
 85. Scott, J.H., Menouar, M.A., & Dunn, R.J. (2023). Physiology, Aldosterone. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470339/>
 86. Sell, J., Ramirez, S., & Partin, M. (2022). Parathyroid Disorders. *American Family Physician*, 105(3), 289–298.
 87. sensing receptor. *American Journal of Medicine*, 106(2), 238-53. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9343\(98\)00418-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9343(98)00418-5)
 88. Shah, M.K., Workeneh, B., & Taffet, G.E. (2014). Hyponatremia in the geriatric population. *Clinical Interventions in Aging*, 9, 1987–1992. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CIA.S65214>
 89. Shah, M.M., & Mandiga, P. (2022). Physiology, Plasma Osmolality and Oncotic Pressure. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK544365/>
 90. Sherwood, L. (2013). *Human Physiology, From Cells to Systems*. Belmont, CA: Brooks/Cole, Cengage Learning.
 91. Shiber, J.R., & Mattu, A. (2002). Serum phosphate abnormalities in the emergency department. *Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 23, 395–400.
 92. Silverthorne, D.U. (2013). *Human Physiology, An Integrated Approach*. Boston, MA: Pearson Education, Inc.
 93. Siuka, D., Rakuša, M., Vodenik, A., Vodnik, L., Štabuc, B., Štubljar, D., Drobne, D., Jerin, A., Matelič, H., & Osredkar, J. (2025). Free and Bioavailable Vitamin D Are Correlated with Disease Severity in Acute Pancreatitis: A Single-Center, Prospective Study. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 26(12), 5695. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms26125695>
 94. Souza, A.C.R., Vasconcelos, A.R., Dias, D.D., Komoni, G., & Name, J.J. (2023). The Integral Role of Magnesium in Muscle Integrity and Aging: A Comprehensive Review. *Nutrients*, 15(24), 5127. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15245127>
 95. Sumi, H., Tominaga, N., Fujita, Y., Verbalis, J. G., & and the Electrolyte Winter Seminar, Collaborative Group (2025). Pathophysiology, symptoms, outcomes, and evaluation of hyponatremia: comprehension and best clinical practice. *Clinical and Experimental Nephrology*, 29(2), 134–148. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10157-025-02624-9>
 96. Sunheimer, R.L., & Graves, L. (2011). *Clinical Laboratory Chemistry*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson, 311-331.
 97. Swaminathan R. (2003). Magnesium metabolism and its disorders. *The Clinical Biochemist. Reviews*, 24(2), 47–66.
 98. Sylow, L., Tokarz, V.L., Richter, E.A., & Klip, A. (2021). The many actions of insulin in skeletal muscle, the paramount tissue determining glycemia. *Cell Metabolism*, 33(4), 758–780. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2021.03.020>
 99. Thu Kyaw, M., & Maung, Z M. (2022). Hypokalemia-Induced Arrhythmia: A Case Series and Literature Review. *Cureus*, 14(3), e22940. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.22940>
 100. Tobias, A., Ballard, B.D., & Mohiuddin, S.S. (2022). Physiology, Water Balance. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK541059/>
 101. Tsilosani, A., Gao, C., & Zhang, W. (2022). Aldosterone-Regulated Sodium Transport and Blood Pressure. *Frontiers in physiology*, 13, 770375. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2022.770375>
 102. Tzamaloukas, A.H., Khitan, Z.J., Glew, R.H., Roumelioti, M.E., Rondon-Berrios, H., Elisaf, M.S., Raj, D.S., Owen, J., Sun, Y., Siamopoulos, K.C., Rohrscheib, M., Ing, T.S., Murata, G.H., Shapiro, J.I., & Malhotra, D. (2019). Serum Sodium Concentration and Tonicity in Hyperglycemic Crises: Major Influences and Treatment Implications. *Journal of the American Heart Association*, 8(19), e011786. <https://doi.org/10.1161/JAHA.118.011786>
 103. Udensi, U.K., & Tchounwou, P.B. (2017). Potassium Homeostasis, Oxidative Stress, and Human Disease. *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Physiology*, 4(3), 111–122. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijcep.ijcep_43_17
 104. Ueda, Y., Ookawara, S., Ito, K., Miyazawa, H., Kaku, Y., Hoshino, T., Tabei, K., & Morishita, Y. (2016). Changes in urinary potassium excretion in patients with chronic kidney disease. *Kidney Research and Clinical Practice*, 35(2), 78–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.krcp.2016.02.001>
 105. Verbrugge, F.H., Steels, P., Grieten, L., Nijst, P., Tang, W.H., & Mullens, W. (2015). Hyponatremia in acute decompensated heart failure: depletion

- versus dilution. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 65(5), 480–492.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2014.12.010>
106. Voltan, G., Cannito, M., Ferrarese, M., Ceccato, F., & Camozzi, V. (2023). Vitamin D: An Overview of Gene Regulation, Ranging from Metabolism to Genomic Effects. *Genes*, 14(9), 1691.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/genes14091691>
107. Warren, A.M., Grossmann, M., Christ-Crain, M., & Russell, N. (2023). Syndrome of Inappropriate Antidiuresis: From Pathophysiology to Management. *Endocrine Reviews*, 44(5), 819–861.
<https://doi.org/10.1210/endrev/bnad010>
108. Weaver, C.M., & Peacock, M. (2019). Calcium. *Advances in nutrition (Bethesda, Md.)*, 10(3), 546–548. <https://doi.org/10.1093/advances/nmy086>
109. Weiss, J.N., Qu, Z., & Shivkumar, K. (2017). Electrophysiology of Hypokalemia and Hyperkalemia. *Circulation. Arrhythmia and Electrophysiology*, 10(3), e004667.
<https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCEP.116.004667>
110. Wikimedia. (2023). Aldosterone feedback loop. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:2711_Aldosterone_Feedback_Loop-01.jpg
111. Wu, A.H.B. (2006). *Clinical Guide to Laboratory Tests*. Philadelphia, Pa: WB Saunders Co., 4th Edition, Pp. 2-29.
112. Yasir, M., & Mechanic, O.J. (2023). Syndrome of Inappropriate Antidiuretic Hormone Secretion. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK507777/>
113. Young, D.S. (1997). *Effects of preanalytical variables on clinical laboratory tests*. Washington, DC: AACC Press, 2nd ed.
114. Yu, E., & Sharma, S. (2023). Physiology, Calcium. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK482128/>